

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of α -Phenyl-2-(2',5'-dihydroxy-3'-bromophenyl)-3-aryl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones, α -Methyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-benzyl)-3-aryl-5-H/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones and α -Methyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-chlorophenyl)-3-aryl-5-H/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones

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4-Thiazolidinones have been prepared for better therapeutic activity by condensing thioglycolic acid and thiomalic acid with anils obtained from 2,5-dihydroxy-3-bromobenzophenone and 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylchloroacetophenones. The constitution was supported by ir spectra and the products were tested for antimicrobial activity.

IN continuation of our work on 4-thiazolidinones, we have prepared α -phenyl-2-(2',5'-dihydroxy-3'-bromophenyl)-3-aryl-5-H/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone (1) by the action of thioglycolic acid and thiomalic acid on Schiff bases which were obtained by condensing 2,5-dihydroxy-3-bromobenzophenone with different aromatic amines. α -Methyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-benzyl)-3-aryl-5-H/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone of type (2) and α -methyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-chlorophenyl)-3-aryl-5-H/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone (2) were prepared by the action of thioglycolic acid thiomalic acid on Schiff bases (1) obtained by the action of different aromatic amines with 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylacetophenone^{2,3} and 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-chloroacetophenone⁴, respectively. The constitution was supported by ir spectra. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup-plate method⁵.

was observed as follow: -N-C- at 1 580 (1), 1 580 (2), C=O at 1 660 (1), 1 650 (2), phenolic OH at 3 300 (1), 3 300 (2), and C-NO₂ (aromatic) at 1 530 cm⁻¹ (2).

Experimental

2,5-Dihydroxy-3-bromobenzophenone anil: Aniline (0.02 mol, 1.85 g) was added to the solution of 2,5-dihydroxy-3-bromobenzophenone (0.02 mol, 5.86 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (75%), m.p. 190° (Found: C, 61.85; H, 3.70; N, 3.68. C₁₃H₁₄NO₂Br required: C, 61.96; H, 3.80; N, 3.80%).

Similarly, other anils were prepared. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

α -Phenyl-2-(2',5'-dihydroxy-3'-bromophenyl)-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones: Thioglycolic acid (0.005 mol, 0.460 g) was added to the solution of 2,5-dihydroxy-3-bromobenzophenone anil (0.005 mol, 1.29 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The contents were cooled, poured in water, the upper organic layer washed with a sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and benzene distilled. The product was crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 360° (Found: C, 57.00; H, 3.61; N, 3.09. C₂₁H₁₆NO₃BrS required: C, 57.01; H, 3.62; N, 3.17%).

Similarly, other anils were condensed Physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

α -Phenyl-2-(2',5'-dihydroxy-3'-bromophenyl)-3-aryl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones: 2,5-Dihydroxy-4-bromophenyl anil (0.005 mol, 1.29 g) was

X = OH, OH₂, Cl
Y = NO₂, Br
Z = OH₂ or phenyl

R = Aryl
R' = H, CH₃, CH₂, COOH

Ir spectra: The ir spectra (KBr) were taken in the range 600 - 4 000 cm⁻¹. The group frequency

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF KETOANILS OF TYPE 1*

Sl. no.	R	X	Y	Z	Molecular formula	M.p °C
1.	Phenyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ Br	190
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ Br	225
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ Br	210
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ Br	180
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ Br	175
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ Br	197
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ Br	210
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ ClBr	160
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ ClBr	200
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ ClBr	230
11.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ Br	200
12.	Phenyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	158
13.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	165
14.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	168
15.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	178
16.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	145
17.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	128
18.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	139
19.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	111
20.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	178
21.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	180
22.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	190
23.	Phenyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	158
24.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	170
25.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	180
26.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	198
27.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	145
28.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	108
29.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	139
30.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	117
31.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	178
32.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	185
33.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	171

* Percentage yield varies from 55 to 78, all compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF THIAZOLIDINONES OF TYPE 2*

Sl. no.	R	R'	X	Y	Z	Molecular formula	M p. °C
1.	Phenyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ BrS	360
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrS	360
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrS	105
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrS	175
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ BrS	360
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ BrS	360
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ BrS	360
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrS	360
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrClS	185
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrClS	190
11.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrClS	228
12.	Phenyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NBrS	270
13.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrS	118
14.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrS	135
15.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrS	158
16.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ BrS	165
17.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ BrS	101
18.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ BrS	115
19.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrS	105
20.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrClS	108
21.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrClS	115
22.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	OH	Br	Ph	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ BrClS	111
23.	Phenyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	125
24.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	95
25.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	100
26.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	125
27.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	130
28.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	110
29.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	140
30.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	145
31.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	90
32.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	145
						C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ ClS	148

(Table 2 contd.)

33.	Phenyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ S	270
34.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ S	90
35.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ S	125
36.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ S	109
37.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₇ S	110
38.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₇ S	265
39.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₇ S	268
40.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	280
41.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	281
42.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	Me	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	285
43.	Phenyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	118
44.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	115
45.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	119
46.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	130
47.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₇ ClS	145
48.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₇ ClS	152
49.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₇ ClS	175
50.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	150
51.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	160
52.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ Cl ₂ S	165
53.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	H	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₂ ClS	160
54.	Phenyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	270
55.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	274
56.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	285
57.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	288
58.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₇ ClS	250
59.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₇ ClS	265
60.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₇ ClS	269
61.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ ClS	230
62.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ Cl ₂ S	235
63.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ Cl ₂ S	281
64.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	CH ₃ COOH	Cl	NO ₂	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₇ ClS	239

* Percentage yield varies from 32 to 78 ; all compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

condensed with thiomalic acid (0.005 mol, 0.750 g) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h as described above. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (32%), m.p. 118° (Found : C, 2.65 ; H, 3.50 ; N, 2.65. C₂₂H₁₈NO₆BrS required : C, 2.80 ; H, 3.60 ; N, 2.80%).

Similarly, other anils were condensed. Physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methyl-acetophenone anil : Aniline (0.01 mol, 1 ml) was added to 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylacetophenone (0.01 mol, 1.83 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 158° (Found : C, 65.27 ; H, 5.00 ; N, 10.80. C₁₄H₁₁N₂O₆ required : C, 65.37 ; H, 5.06 ; N, 10.89%).

Similarly, other anils were prepared. Physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

α -Methyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-methylphenyl)-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones : Thioglycolic acid (0.005 mol, 0.460 g) was condensed with 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylacetophenone anil (0.005 mol, 1.0 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) as described in the second method. The product was crystallised from ethanol, (42%), m.p. 95° (Found : C, 57.92 ; H, 4.48 ; N, 8.30. C₁₆H₁₅N₂O₄S required : C, 58.01, H, 4.53 ; N, 8.46%).

The other anils were similarly condensed. Physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

α -Methyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-methylphenyl)-3-aryl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones : 2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylacetophenone anil (0.005 mol, 1.08 g) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.005 mol, 0.750 g) as described in the second method. The product was crystallised from ethanol, (30%), m.p. 270° (Found : C, 55.55 ; H, 4.28 ; N, 7.11. C₁₈H₁₇N₂O₆S required : C, 55.53 ; H, 4.37 ; N, 7.20%).

Similarly, other anils were condensed. Physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-5-chloroacetophenone anil : Aniline (0.02 mol, 1.8 g) was added to 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-chloroacetophenone (0.02 mol, 4.3 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The products was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 158° (Found : C, 57.70 ; H, 3.74 ; N, 9.50. C₁₄H₁₁N₂O₄Cl required : C, 57.83 ; H, 3.79 ; N, 9.63%).

Similarly, other anils were condensed. Physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

α -Methyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-chlorophenyl)-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones : Thioglycolic acid (0.005 mol, 0.460 g) was condensed with 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-chloroacetophenone anil (0.005 mol, 0.7 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) as described in the second method. The product was crystallised from ethanol, (40%),

m.p. 110° (Found : C, 52.60 ; H, 3.53 ; N, 7.53, $C_{18}H_{13}N_2O_4ClS$ required : C, 52.68 ; H, 3.57 ; N, 7.68%).

Similarly, other anils were condensed. Physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

α -Methyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-chlorophenyl)-3-aryl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones : 2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-5-chloroacetophenone anil (0.005 mol, 0.1 g) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.005 mol, 0.750 g) as described in the second method. The product was crystallised from ethanol, (30%), m.p. 270° (Found : C, 51.00 ; H, 3.49 ; N, 6.50. $C_{18}H_{13}N_2O_6ClS$ required : C, 51.12 ; H, 3.55 ; N, 6.63%).

Similarly, other anils were condensed. Physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

Antimicrobial screening : Purified products were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive

bacteria, i.e. *S. aureus*, and gram-negative bacteria, i.e. *E. coli* and *S. typhosa*. The testing was carried out in dioxan at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The zone of inhibition of the test solution (0.05 mg) are recorded. From the experimental data it was observed that in thiazolidinone of type 2, the condensation products with thiomalic acid are more active as compared to anils (1). The zone of inhibition in case of the anils varied from 15–20 mm while in case of thiazolidinone it varied from 15 to 25 mm.

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